

ISic1245

I.Sicily inscription 1245

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140730

1. ΛCO#⁷#⁵⁶#⁷ [— — — — —]

2. νιδίϛ σ[υ]νβί [ωχρηστῆ]

3. κὲ ἀ[μ]έμπτ[ω].

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492848

EDCS 39101610

PHI 140730

Bibliography

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